

Privation of Memory: What can be done to help stroke patients remember?

Weakness, pain, swallowing difficulties; many patients are aware of these common post-stroke physical symptoms. However, stroke can also affect thinking abilities, or cognition. Cognition can be thought of as how people use their brains to talk, read, write, learn, understand, and remember. Approximately one third of stroke victims will develop memory problems. Losing skills in this area may affect ability to conduct activities of daily living and thus the ability to live independently. This publication serves to provide background information on memory loss after stroke and actions to implement that may improve memory.

Why does memory loss occur?

Memory loss commonly occurs as a result of the loss of nerve cells in the brain. When memory loss is so severe that it interferes with normal daily functioning, it is called dementia. People with dementia may have difficulty learning new things or remembering names. They may get lost in places that were previously familiar or have trouble finding words.

When dementia occurs after a stroke and no other cause can be found it is called vascular dementia, resulting from stroke brain damage. Both large strokes and multiple small strokes can cause vascular dementia. Conditions such as old age, prior memory problems, a history of several strokes, or a stroke located in the left side of the brain all seem to increase the likelihood of dementia in the first year after stroke.

How is memory affected?

What stroke does to memory depends on where and how the stroke injured the brain plus the overall health of the patient. Each side of the brain controls different things. A stroke on one side of the brain will cause different problems than a stroke on the other side. This means that memory loss will not be the same for each stroke patient. Two types of memory that can be affected by stroke include the following:

- Verbal memory – memory of names, stories and information having to do with words
- Visual memory – memory of faces, shapes, routes and things seen

What are the symptoms?

The symptoms of memory loss and vascular dementia include slow movement and thinking, lack of attention, and inability to do simple tasks. Symptoms of dementia after stroke can be hidden by more obvious post stroke conditions such as paralysis, blindness, or depression.

Are there any treatments or medications to help?

There are no specific medical treatments to help reverse the memory loss that occurs after a stroke. Neurologists sometimes prescribe medications approved for Alzheimer's dementia for people with vascular dementia, but the usefulness of these medications in patients with vascular dementia is still unknown. Therapies or medicines almost never fully restore memory after stroke. However, many people do recover at least some memory spontaneously after stroke. Others improve through rehabilitation. Successful rehabilitation depends on:

- Amount of damage to the brain
- Cooperation of patient's caregivers
- Skill of the rehabilitation team
- Onset of rehabilitation– the earlier it begins the more likely lost abilities and skills can be regained

The goal of rehabilitation is to enable an individual who has experienced a stroke to reach the highest possible level of independence and be as productive as possible. Because stroke survivors often have complex rehabilitation needs, progress and recovery are unique for each person. Although a majority of functional abilities may be restored soon after a stroke, recovery is an ongoing process.

Any other suggestions to help with memory loss?

- Form a routine by doing certain tasks at regular times during the day

PUBLIC FORUM

Jill Novitzke, RN

Address correspondence to:
Jill Novitzke, RN, Zeenat Qureshi
Stroke Research Center, Department
of Neurology, University of
Minnesota, 420 Delaware St SE,
Minneapolis, MN 55455
novit001@umn.edu

- Break down tasks into simple steps
- Make a habit of always putting things away in the same place where they can be easily seen or found
- Associate names with a famous person or someone already known
- Form a picture in the mind of the things to remember
Bizarre images are remembered better, so incorporate unusual ideas in mind pictures
- Jot down notes of what needs to be done or complete tasks right away
- Repeat and study information such as dates and directions over and over
- Seek the help of a neuropsychologist and/or a speech pathologist

How can memory loss be prevented?

The best way to prevent dementia after stroke is to avoid having a stroke in the first place. Controlling high blood pressure can dramatically reduce the risk of having a stroke. Regular check-ups, exercise, a healthy diet, quitting smoking, plus maintaining a normal cholesterol and blood sugar level can also reduce stroke risk and the resultant possible memory loss.

Sources

- American Stroke Association
- National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke
- National Stroke Association
- Patient page. Memory loss after stroke. *Neurology*. 2006 Oct 24;67(8):E14-5